

GS 79
SPHINX
June 25, 1979

Living Floor fronting Amenhotep II Temple - Dump clearing

Material from the dump of NS 78 operations, at the SW front corner of the Amenhotep II Temple, was used for refilling the trench of R2. This seems to have broken into the sand (w. mud spots) foundation of the alluvial mud "living floor" along the front of the Amenhotep Temple. ("Living floor" in that Salim Hassan found indications of its use as such). I noticed from down in the sanctuary that the refilling material looked to be clean tan sand, and thought they may be in the material from the excavation of locus 4 in R6 - clean sand layer. But they seemed to have broken into the sand foundation of the "living floor" (which may be contemporary with locus 4 in R6?). M. Laafi had saved out 1 large painted body sherd, with black decorative lines on red ware, and also a large piece of a thin walled bowl vessel with black band on the rim (red ware), almost the same as a piece from R6 locus 4. There was also retrieved a worked flint (scraper?). I told them only to clear down at the location of the dump as far as the grey sand clearly from the excavations of last year.